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MAKHALLA - THE DISAPPEARING HISTORICAL APPEARANCE OF OLD TASHKENT

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**The neighborhood is the foundation of our eternal value,
rich past and bright future.**

Abstract: In this article, many people think that Tashkent is too Europeanized, but not everyone knows that in the very center of the city today there are national, colorful, charming neighborhoods - traditional Uzbek neighborhoods, where there are generous one- and two-story houses that have stood here for more than a hundred years...

New houses are emerging today in place of the destroyed neighborhoods. The residents of the neighborhoods will probably live in them more comfortably, but soon, unfortunately, there will be no trace of the unique appearance of old Tashkent.

Key words: city, city center, neighborhood, tradition, mosque, madrasa, people and state, market, personal self-government bodies

The experience of state structure and management in the Asian continent and the Muslim East has its own characteristics and traditions. A neighborhood that existed before the Arab conquest and the conversion to Islam existed as an association of people living in a certain small area, bound not only by good neighborly relations, but also by internal rules of conduct. spiritual and moral standards, customs and traditions formed over the centuries. This type of socio-economic harmony of the population changes at each stage of historical development. Socio-political, cultural and economic changes came to most traditional Uzbek families through the neighborhood.

Tashkent, in the minds of many, is a completely Europeanized capital of Uzbekistan with wide avenues, green parks and beautiful high-rises built in recent

years. However, not everyone knows that almost in the very center of the city, charming corners of national color have been preserved to this day - traditional Uzbek mahalla quarters, adobe one- and two-story houses of which have been standing here for more than a hundred years...

In Tashkent, not far from the Chorsu market, there is a circus. It is no coincidence that this place is located this way: it was here that the center of the old city was once located. Since the Middle Ages, ancient mosques and madrassas have been preserved here, such as, for example, the famous Kukeldash, here was the Tashkent shakhristan - a part of the city with residential areas inside the fortress wall.

Not many tourists today reach the Zarkaynar district, located behind the circus, but it is here that you can still see the unique adobe houses of local mahallas, which now look the same as they did 100-150 years ago.

These are old Uzbek quarters of 5-7 streets and several hundred residents, where there is a mosque, a small market, a teahouse and tiny mahalla committee offices headed by their elder. Completely different people live here than in the modern microdistricts of Tashkent, and for tourists who have come here, the medieval appearance of these streets complements the "ethnographic" appearance of Tashkent.

In the mahalla, every resident knows not only all of their closest neighbors, but also Aunt Khadicha from the Sagban dead end, who cooks the most delicious pilaf in the mahalla, and the hairdresser Baykhtiyer, who gets all the men in the quarter cut off. Here, children calmly ride their bikes through the streets, just like we did in

our Soviet childhood. And the neighboring grandmothers treat them to samsa or flatbreads, just taken out of the oven.

Even today, you can easily see chickens, rams or goats in the courtyards of old adobe houses - and this is actually in the center of the capital of Uzbekistan! Tashkent, in the minds of many, is a completely Europeanized capital of Uzbekistan with wide avenues, green parks and beautiful high-rises built in recent years.

Tashkent Kukeldash: people studied, prayed, and maintained a caravanserai here.

However, not everyone knows that almost in the very center of the city, charming corners of national color have been preserved to this day - traditional Uzbek mahalla neighborhoods, whose adobe one- and two-story houses have been standing here for over a hundred years...

Local boys also like to run to the Khazrati Imam religious complex located next to the mahalla, where on the square between the ancient mosque of the same name and two madrassas - Barakhan and Muyi Muborak, they launch kites into the sky, just like their fathers and grandfathers did 30-50 years ago...

Tourists who come to see this stunningly beautiful architectural ensemble love to stare at the kites soaring in the blue sky, and the kids who are especially skilled at this craft sometimes get a few sums for pocket money...

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Now you can see the Khazrati Imam Complex and the Zarkaynar mahalla nearby. Of course, not everywhere here today is so relatively welcoming and calm: part of the quarter has been under reconstruction, which has been going on for ten years, and the old houses there are being torn down, and the residents are being evicted to modern high-rise buildings.

Some of them still continue to live in half-ruined adobe houses, which are separated from the modern microdistricts of the city by a high fence - like some kind of reservation of local "Indians". I think that the attitude of Tashkent residents to the residents of the mahalla is something else - as to third-class people, because who else would live in such slums in our time...

By the way, houses in the mahalla are still being built using old Uzbek technology, which saved many buildings in its time from the strongest earthquake of 1966, which greatly destroyed Tashkent.

Houses are built using natural materials: an internal wooden frame is installed from the trunks of young pyramidal poplars, which makes the entire structure strong and earthquake-resistant. Bricks are partially laid inside the frame, but mostly guval - pellets of unbaked clay. The walls of houses in the mahalla are usually made blind on three sides. And inside the clay duval there is an internal courtyard with a garden and outbuildings.

When building houses, as a rule, not a single nail is used, since the wooden parts fit perfectly to each other.

On the facade of the house there are one or two windows with carved wooden frames, the entrance gates are usually also wooden, often carved.

Water and gas pipes do not run underground in the mahalla, but hang along the streets, along with electrical wires.

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Back in 2012, former President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov signed a decree on the reconstruction, improvement and development of the old city in Tashkent,

during which, in addition to the restoration of mosques and madrassas, the dilapidated adobe buildings that were erected in Tashkent even before Tsarist Russia conquered Central Asia in the 19th century were to be demolished!

Since then, many mahalla buildings have been demolished, and some are still awaiting this fate, because next to the religious complex of Hazrati Imam in 2017, the new President Shavkat Mirziyoyev laid the symbolic stone of the future giant building of the Center for Islamic Civilization. Passing by it, we could not help but look at the construction site, which is in full swing. A grand mosque will soon appear there, the dome of which is in no way inferior in beauty to ancient monuments. And nearby, on an area of 482 hectares, including the Chorsu market, the streets of the mahallas "Zarkaynar", "Sagbon", "Sebzor", "Karasaray", "Guzalbog" and others, it is planned to create a tourist, commercial and entertainment space - the so-called open-air museum, where craft workshops and shops, teahouses, hotels, small museums will be organized, in general, all the necessary infrastructure for tourists.

New houses are appearing today on the site of the demolished neighborhoods. The former residents of the mahallas will live in them, perhaps, more comfortably, but soon, unfortunately, there will be no trace left of the unique appearance of old Tashkent.

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